

Supporting Information

DOM offsets the detrimental effects of climate change in the nitrogen fixing cyanobacterium *Crocospaera*

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Supplementary Methods

Cultures growth and acclimation

Batch cultures of *Crocospaera watsonii* WH8501 (Waterbury and Rippka, 1989) (hereafter *Crocospaera*) were grown in 0.2 µm-filtered seawater based nitrogen-free YBC-II medium (Chen et al. 1996) at 26°C under a 12 h light :12 h dark cycle and a daytime photon flux of ~250 µmol photons m⁻² s⁻¹. The cultures were gradually adapted to lower phosphate concentrations than the usual phosphate YBC-II medium composition for eight weeks (~25 µM final concentration). Four weeks prior to the experiment, the cultures were acclimated to three temperature and pH target levels, i.e. 26°C and pH 8.1, 28°C and pH 8.0 and, 30°C and pH 7.9, corresponding to IPCC scenarios RCP 2.6, 4.5 and 6.0 (IPCC, 2014), i.e., low, intermediate and extreme treatments. For the thermal acclimation, temperature was increased from 26°C until reaching temperatures of 28°C and 30°C at a rate of 0.5°C per day for eight days. New parent cultures from the temperature-acclimated cultures were prepared by bubbling with CO₂ to reach the target pH levels (8.1, 8.0 and 7.9) and grown for another seven days (~four generations) before starting the experiment in larger volumes.

Experimental setup

Acclimated *Crocospaera* cultures were transferred to 40 L cylindric transparent methacrylate tanks ([10.6084/m9.figshare.22773503](https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.22773503)) and mixed with YBC-II medium prepared as described above to achieve a starting concentration of $\sim 1.5 \times 10^4$ cells mL⁻¹. Two tanks were used as low treatment (26°C, pH 8.1), three as intermediate treatment (28°C, pH 8.0), and three as extreme treatment (30°C, pH 7.9) ([10.6084/m9.figshare.22773503](https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.22773503)). The experiment was run for eight days (days -2 to 5) under a 12 h light :12 h dark cycle simulating sunrise and sunset light shifts (Alpheus LED lamps, Montgeron, France). The negative day values (days -2 to 0) correspond to the post-acclimation period, when *Crocospaera* cells are transferred from concentrated cultures to the larger tanks, while positive day values (days 0 to 5) correspond to the experimental period. The temperature and pH levels of each set of tanks was maintained at their corresponding values using an IKS aquastar system (IKS Aquastar Computer System GmbH, Karlsbad, Germany). Briefly, the IKS system autonomously measures and adjusts the target temperature and pH levels by switching on and off thermostats and the inlet of CO₂ gas (CO₂ \geq 99,9 %, Alphagaz, Air Liquide, Metz, France) when the associated temperature and pH sensors go out of range.

Over the eight days of the experiment, samples were taken on a daily basis to measure *Crocospaera* cell abundance, salinity, temperature, pH and carbonate chemistry, as well as nitrate, ammonium and phosphate concentrations (see below). On alternate days (days 0, 2 and 4), subsamples were taken to measure N₂ and DIC fixation, DOM uptake and sample for RNA (see below). Before each sampling time point, the tanks were gently homogenized with a custom-made stirrer to minimise cell adhesion to the tank walls and/or sedimentation, and gentle air bubbling (one bubble every two seconds) also prevented stratification inside the tanks ([10.6084/m9.figshare.22773503](https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.22773503)).

Core parameters

Discrete measurements of temperature, pH and salinity were performed on a daily basis sampling or submerging the sensors into the tanks to follow the constancy of the target levels (treatments) and the potential evaporation, respectively. Temperature and salinity were measured with a conductivity-salinity-temperature meter YSI Pro30 (Xylem, Inc., New York, USA). For pH measurements, samples from each tank were collected into 10 cm cylindrical optical glass cells (120-OS.100, Hellma, Paris, France). The pH measurement principle is based on the dissociation of a pH-sensitive dye in the water sample. Here, analyses were performed manually using purified m-Cresol Purple following the spectrophotometric protocol described by Clayton and Byrne (1993). Samples were beforehand set to 25°C (+/-0.1°C) and maintained at that temperature during spectrophotometric analysis. Absorbances

at three wavelengths were measured with a Carry 60 instrument (Agilent, Santa Clara, USA). pH is reported on the total scale using the equation by Liu et al. (2011). The accuracy of the method was verified by analysing certified TRIS solutions (provided by Scripps Institution of Oceanography). Measurements did not differ from more than 0.005 pH units from the certified value. Concentrations of CO₂ and other carbonate system parameters were calculated from discrete spectrophotometric pH, a constant total alkalinity from the source water (2650 μmol kg⁻¹) and the correspondent temperature and salinity values using the *seacarb* R package ([10.6084/m9.figshare.22773503](https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.22773503)). Total alkalinity was determined on triplicate 50 mL subsamples by potentiometric titration on a 888 Titrand titrator coupled to a glass electrode plus (Metrohm, France) and a pt1000 thermometer, and calculated as described by Dickson et al. (2007). Using standards provided by A. Dickson the precision (the standard deviation within measurements of the same batch) and accuracy (deviation from the certified value provided by A. Dickson) were calculated. The precision and accuracy were 1.95 and 0.51 μmol kg⁻¹, respectively (n = 3).

Samples for the measurement of nitrate, phosphate, dissolved organic phosphorus and nitrogen concentrations were collected every morning after GF/F filtration for each tank and stored at -20°C until analysis. Concentrations of the inorganic nutrients were determined using a segmented flow analyzer (AAIII HR, Seal Analytical) according to Aminot and Krouel (2007). Total dissolved phosphorus and nitrogen concentrations were analyzed by high-temperature (120°C) persulfate wet oxidation mineralization (Pujo-Pay and Raimbault, 1994), and subtracting phosphate and nitrate concentrations to the total dissolved phosphorus and nitrogen concentrations we obtained the correspondent dissolved organic fraction. The quantification limits were 0.05 μM for nitrate and 0.02 μM for phosphate, dissolved organic phosphorus and nitrogen. The precision and accuracy, linked to the repeatability of the standards measurements and uncertainty of the calibration curve slope was of 1.06% and 1.01% for dissolved nitrogen (n = 8), and 0.98% and 0.13% for dissolved phosphorus (n = 8), respectively.

N₂ fixation, DIC fixation and DOM uptake rates

Single-cell N₂ fixation, and DIC fixation and DOM uptake rates were measured from 64 mL subsamples taken from each tank on days 0, 2 and 4. N₂ fixation was measured by adding 6 mL of pre-dissolved ¹⁵N₂ gas (98.9 atom%, Euroiso-top) in the incubation bottles (adapted from Montoya et al. 1996). The pre-dissolved source of ¹⁵N₂ was prepared in YBC-II medium in the same proportions and pH levels as in the incubation bottles. DIC fixation was measured by adding 70 μL of ¹³C-HCO₃ (0.1 M C, Sigma-Aldrich, Hamburg, Germany) and DOM uptake by adding 16 μL of a ¹³C-DOM mix (¹³C-99 atom%, Eurisotop, Saint-Aubin, France) at a final concentration of 20 μM C, i.e. 10% of the dissolved organic carbon concentration in YBC-II medium. The amended ¹³C-DOM was prepared by mixing fully ¹³C-labelled organic compounds including amino acids – 22% L-Alanine, 28% L-Leucine and 18% L-

Arginine- and carbohydrates - 24% glucose and 8% N-acetylglucosamine - (carbon molar %). The amino acids alanine, leucine and arginine are typically found in the labile fraction of oceanic DOM (Keil and Kirchman 1991a). Glucose is found across oceanic regions where diazotrophs such as *Crocospaera* are present, including the Sargasso Sea and the Equatorial Pacific Ocean (Borch and Kirchman 1997; Skoog and Benner, 1997), and N-acetylglucosamine is a basic unit of chitin and among the largest pools of amino sugars in the ocean (Gooday 1990; Riemann and Azam 2002). Incubations were done at the temperature and pH conditions corresponding to each treatment, under a 12:12 h light:dark cycle for 24 h. After incubation, 12 mL of the sample were collected in gas tight exetainers to measure the $^{15}\text{N}/^{14}\text{N}$ ratio in the dissolved N_2 pool using a membrane inlet mass spectrometer (MIMS, Kana et al. 1994). The precision of the dissolved $^{15}\text{N}_2$ atom% measured by MIMS averaged 0.01 atom% in our analyses and the standard deviation among incubation replicates was not higher than 0.2 atom%. The incubation volume remaining after MIMS sampling (about 50 mL) was filtered through 0.2 μm polycarbonate filters, fixed with 1.6% paraformaldehyde and stored at -80°C until further analysis.

The $^{13}\text{C}/^{12}\text{C}$ and $^{15}\text{N}/^{14}\text{N}$ ratios of single *Crocospaera* cells were analysed with a 50L Cameca nanoscale secondary ion mass spectrometer (nanoSIMS) at the Leibniz Institute for Baltic Sea Research (IOW, Warnemünde, Germany). Before measurements, portions of polycarbonate filters were mounted on 10 x 5 mm aluminum stubs (Ted Pella, Redding, CA, USA) using conductive copper tape and gold-coated to a thickness of ca. 30 nm (Cressington 108 auto sputter coater). The analyses were performed. A 1 pA 16 keV Cesium (Cs^+) primary beam was scanned on a 512×512 pixel raster with a raster area of $45 \times 45 \mu\text{m}$, and a counting time of 250 μs per pixel. Prior to analyses, samples were pre-sputtered with 600 pA Cs^+ current for five to ten minutes in a raster of $50 \times 50 \mu\text{m}$ to remove the gold and surface contaminants and reach the steady state of ion formation. Negative secondary ions $^{12}\text{C}^-$, $^{13}\text{C}^-$, $^{12}\text{C}^{14}\text{N}^-$, $^{12}\text{C}^{15}\text{N}^-$, $^{31}\text{P}^-$ and $^{32}\text{S}^-$ were detected with electron multiplier detectors (Hamamatsu, Herrsching am Ammersee, Germany), and secondary electrons were simultaneously imaged. Sixty serial quantitative secondary ion mass planes were generated, drift corrected and accumulated to the final image. Mass resolving power was >8000 (Cameca's definition) in order to resolve isobaric interferences. Data was processed using the Look@nanoSIMS software (Polerecky et al. 2012). Isotope ratio images were generated by dividing the ion counts of $^{13}\text{C}^-$ by $^{12}\text{C}^-$, and $^{12}\text{C}^{15}\text{N}^-$ by $^{12}\text{C}^{14}\text{N}^-$ pixel by pixel. *Crocospaera* cells were identified in the nanoSIMS secondary electron $^{12}\text{C}^{14}\text{N}^-$ and $^{31}\text{P}^-$ images which were used to define the regions of interest (ROIs). For each ROI, the $^{13}\text{C}/(^{12}\text{C}+^{13}\text{C})$ and $^{15}\text{N}/(^{14}\text{N}+^{15}\text{N})$ ratios were calculated based on the ion counts averaged over the ROIs. The analytical precision of the isotopic percent abundances was 0.005 and 0.022 atom% for N and C, respectively. Cellular ^{13}C and ^{15}N atom % enrichment after 24 h incubations were used to measure cell-specific DIC fixation, DOM uptake and N_2 fixation rates in the different treatments. A minimum of 20 cells were measured for three different treatments (1a, 2b and 3c) at three time points (days 0, 2 and 4).

Cell-specific rates were calculated as follows:

$$\frac{A_{cell} - A_{Nat}}{A_{source} - A_{Nat}} \times \frac{1}{t} \times \frac{C \text{ (or } N)}{cell}$$

where A_{cell} is the ^{13}C or ^{15}N atom% enrichment of individual *Crocospaera* cells, A_{Nat} is the natural ^{13}C or ^{15}N atom% enrichment measured in cells at time zero, A_{source} is the ^{13}C or ^{15}N atom% enrichment of the amended ^{13}C -DOM or $^{15}\text{N}_2$, t is the incubation time and C (or N) is the carbon or nitrogen content of single *Crocospaera* cells. The rates obtained have units of $\text{fmol C (or N) cell}^{-1} \text{d}^{-1}$. The carbon content of *Crocospaera* cells was obtained from cell biovolume derived from its equivalent spherical diameter (Sun and Liu, 2003) directly measured on the nanoSIMS images and using a volumetric carbon content of $360 \text{ fg C } \mu\text{m}^{-3}$ according to Verity et al. (1992). The cell nitrogen content was calculated assuming an average C/N ratio of 5.5 (Dekazemacker and Bonnet, 2011; Knapp et al. 2012).

The ^{13}C -DOM A_{source} was calculated based on the volume and concentration of the added substrate (^{13}C -DOM mix) and the background DOC concentrations at every treatment and time point as follows:

$$A_{source} = \frac{\left(\frac{V^{13}\text{C} \times DO^{13}\text{C}}{V_b} \right) + DOC_i \times 0.01112}{DOC_i - \frac{V^{13}\text{C} \times DO^{13}\text{C}}{V_b}} \times 100$$

Where $V^{13}\text{C}$ is the volume of tracer added (here $16 \mu\text{L}$), $DO^{13}\text{C}$ is the concentration of added ^{13}C -DOC (here = $80000 \mu\text{M C}$), DOC_i the initial concentration of DOC (calculated from each tank before incubation, see table below), V_b is the volume of the incubation (here $64000 \mu\text{L}$) and 0.01112 the natural abundance of ^{13}C (%).

RNA sampling, sequencing and bioinformatics

RNA samples were obtained from one same tank of each replicate treatment set at the same time as sampling for single cell rates (see above). From each treatment, three bottles ($\sim 320 \text{ mL}$) were amended with $80 \mu\text{L}$ of $0.08 \text{ M } ^{13}\text{C}$ -DOM mix (final concentration $20 \mu\text{M C}$) and the other three were kept as unamended controls. The six bottles were incubated in separate incubators with temperature and light conditions as in the original experiment. The incubations stopped before 09:00 h in the next morning ($\sim 18 \text{ h}$ incubation). Thus, RNA samples represented the expression profiles of *Crocospaera* at sunrise, where for example photosynthesis genes show their maximum expression (Wilson et al. 2017). In this way, gene expression of pathways for inorganic versus organic carbon cycling and acquisition can be contrasted with each other and compared with the associated physiological responses (inorganic carbon

uptake rates versus DOC). The content of the incubation bottles was filtered onto 0.2 µm polyethylene Supor filters and stored in RNAlater, flash-frozen and stored at -80°C until RNA extractions. RNA was extracted using the RNeasy Mini Kit (Qiagen Sciences, MD, USA) with β-mercaptoethanol (M6250, Sigma Aldrich, Hamburg, Germany) added to the kit's lysis buffer to enhance intracellular RNase denaturation (Moisander et al. 2008). Prior to extraction, filters were ground and submitted to five to ten flash freezing steps with liquid nitrogen to maximise the extraction yield. An extra DNase treatment was performed using the TURBO DNA-free™ Kit (Ambion, Thermo Fisher Scientific), followed by a Zymo-5 column clean up kit (Zymo Research, USA). RNA was quantified using the RiboGreen RNA Quantification Kit (Invitrogen, Thermo Fisher Scientific).

The quality of the raw reads was assessed using the FastQC v0.11.9 toolkit (Andrews 2010). NexteraPE Adapters and low-quality reads were trimmed using Trimmomatic v0.39 (Bolger et al. 2014). Ribosomal RNA fragments were filtered out using the 16S reference sequences from the SILVA database (Pruesse et al. 2007) (release 132: SSU Ref NR 90) with the SortMeRNA v4.3.4 tool (Kopylova et al. 2012). We used MicrobeAnnotator v2.0.5 (Ruiz-Perez et al. 2021) to update the functional annotation of *Crocospaera watsonii* WH8501 genes (downloaded from JGI Genome Portal, GenBank GI #67858163). Kofam (date: April 27, 2022) (Aramaki et al. 2020), UniProt's Swissprot, trEMBL (date: January 2022) (UniProt C. 2019) and NCBI's RefSeq (release 211) (O'Leary et al. 2016) databases were used to annotate the proteins by using Diamond (Buchfin et al. 2015) as a parameter in the `microbeannotator_db_builder` script. The non-rRNA reads were aligned with HiSat2 v2.2.1 (Kim et al. 2015) using default options and gene counts were quantified using feature Counts from the Subread v2.0.1 package (Liao et al. 2019). Alignment and gene counts were generated against the reference genome *Crocospaera watsonii* WH8501. The low expressed genes, which did not have more than one count per million reads (1CPM) in at least three samples within each dataset, were removed from further analysis. Gene counts were then normalized and used for differential expression testing using DESeq2 v1.28.0 (Love et al. 2014).

Statistical analyses

RStudio (RRID: SCR_000432, Version 1.3.1093) was used to process data and to produce graphs. Differences between treatments and time points were evaluated by one-way ANOVA, after checking data for normality and heterogeneity of variance (QQ plot, Shapiro-Wilk test and Levene's test) or with the Kruskal–Wallis test when the data distribution was not normal. Paired *t*-test was applied to compare differences between DOM-amended and unamended conditions. Statistical significance for all tests including differential gene expression analysis was accepted for p-values lower than 0.01 (99% of confidence level).

Supplementary Results

Core parameters

Figures describing the experimental setup and measurements basic experimental parameters (temperature, salinity, pH, inorganic and organic nutrient concentrations, which are shared with a companion paper (Umbricht et al. in prep.) are available in the Figshare repository ([10.6084/m9.figshare.22773503](https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.22773503)).

Salinity did not change significantly along the experiment and the $p\text{CO}_2$ levels fluctuated along the experiment but kept differential levels among treatments ([10.6084/m9.figshare.22773503](https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.22773503)). Phosphate concentrations did not vary with time, indicating no limitation ([10.6084/m9.figshare.22773503](https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.22773503)). Nitrate and ammonium concentrations were below the detection limit throughout the experiment until day 4, when nitrate levels increased to $\sim 0.5 \mu\text{M}$ in all treatments possibly associated with the decay of cells and consequent heterotrophic bacteria remineralization ([10.6084/m9.figshare.22773503](https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.22773503)). Dissolved organic nitrogen fluctuated between 7 and 9 μM along the experiment with slightly faster consumption observed in the low treatment ([10.6084/m9.figshare.22773503](https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.22773503)). Dissolved organic phosphorus decreased after day 0 and remained stable until the end of the experiment with no significant difference among treatments and reflecting rapid consumption and a preference for organic over inorganic phosphorus ([10.6084/m9.figshare.22773503](https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.22773503)).

DOC concentrations were elevated since the beginning of the experiment (*data not shown*) as expected due to the EDTA contents of the YBC-II media to keep iron bioavailable. DOC concentrations increased slightly with time, particularly in the low and extreme treatments (ca. 28 and 21%, respectively), possibly related with the highest cell mortality in these two treatments. However, heterotrophic bacteria abundance did not vary between treatments nor correlated with DOC concentrations, indicating the amended and potentially released DOC by decaying cells was not very labile and did not influence the response of *Crocospaera* to the different treatments and conditions.

N₂ fixation, DIC fixation and DOM uptake

We observed a lower percentage of active cells in the extreme treatment suggesting that cells were unable to keep high metabolic rates for extended periods of time. For example, in the extreme treatment only 45% and 18% of cells actively fixed DIC and N₂ on day 4, compared to day 2 when 65% and 53% actively fixed DIC and N₂, respectively (Fig. S3A). In comparison, 96 and 100% of the cells were actively fixing DIC and N₂ in the intermediate treatment on day 4 (Fig. S3A).

Differential gene expression

The expression of genes involved in essential metabolic function (Table S1) were investigated and contrasted between treatments and sampling time points (Fig. S3). N₂ fixation genes were significantly more expressed in the low treatment than in the other treatments on day 2. Yet on day 4, N₂ fixation genes showed higher expression in the extreme treatment (Fig. S3, Fig.1B). Light-harvesting genes were significantly less expressed in the low treatment than in the intermediate treatment on days 2 and 4, while in the extreme treatment the expression of these genes remained high on day 2 and decreased on day 4 (Fig. S3). Genes related to photosystems I and II were highly expressed in the extreme treatment on day 2, while their expression decreased similarly in all treatments on day 4 (Fig. S4). Other protein complexes that contribute to energy metabolism are ATP synthase and cytochrome b6-f, which mediate linear and cyclic electron transport while pumping protons and creating the electrochemical gradient necessary to generate ATP (Mitchell 1961; Vermaas 2001). The expression of ATP synthase genes was particularly lower in the extreme treatment than in the other two treatments on day 4, suggesting that cells were energy-limited towards the end of the experiment as they decayed faster than in the other treatments (Fig. 1A; Fig. S3). Cytochrome b6-f genes were similarly expressed between treatments and time points (Fig. S3). In the same lines, central carbon pathways such as glycolysis implicated in catabolizing stored carbohydrates to provide energy, resources and metabolites precursors for other key metabolisms showed similar expression among treatments and over time (Fig. S3). Our results show little variation in expression of the core carbon genes with changing conditions or growth curve phase of *Crocospaera*, suggesting that they are either unaffected by the treatments or that the cells can maintain similar expression levels despite significant environmental change.

Interestingly, the expression of most genes which decreased between days 2 and 4 under unamended conditions increased as soon as DOM was added (compare Fig. S4 and Fig. 4), including components of photosystem I, cytochrome b6-f and ATP synthase. Again confirming the role of DOM in increasing the expression of energy-generating machinery under unfavorable conditions, partially sustained by glycolytic pathways (Fig. 4). In contrast, stress-induced proteins increased after DOM additions at the extreme treatment on day 4, despite the DOM benefits at increasing cell-specific N₂ fixation (Fig. 3B).

Thus, longer incubations are required to verify whether osmotrophy could compensate for long exposure to future adverse conditions. Alternatively, gene expression results might be biased by the high intrapopulation variability observed here (Fig. 2; Fig. S2) which was not accounted for with bulk RNA analysis.

Supplementary Tables

Table S1. Annotation information for the genes analysed in this study corresponding to essential metabolic and cellular functions.

query_id	ko	gene_id	Metabolic & cellular functions
2606918843	K02133	ATPeF1B, ATP5B, ATP2; F-type H ⁺ -transporting ATPase subunit beta [EC:7.1.2.2]	ATP synthase
2606914794	K02108	ATPF0A, <i>atpB</i> ; F-type H ⁺ -transporting ATPase subunit a	ATP synthase
2606914799	K02111	ATPF1A, <i>atpA</i> ; F-type H ⁺ /Na ⁺ -transporting ATPase subunit alpha [EC:7.1.2.2 7.2.2.1]	ATP synthase
2606918842	K02114	ATPF1E, <i>atpC</i> ; F-type H ⁺ -transporting ATPase subunit epsilon	ATP synthase
2606914800	K02115	ATPF1G, <i>atpG</i> ; F-type H ⁺ -transporting ATPase subunit gamma	ATP synthase
2606914798	K02121	ATPVE, <i>ntpE</i> , <i>atpE</i> ; V/A-type H ⁺ /Na ⁺ -transporting ATPase subunit E	ATP synthase
2606915124	K08696	<i>ccmK</i> ; carbon dioxide concentrating mechanism protein CcmK	CCM
2606915125	K08696	<i>ccmK</i> ; carbon dioxide concentrating mechanism protein CcmK	CCM
2606920148	K11953	<i>cmpD</i> ; bicarbonate transport system ATP-binding protein [EC:7.3.2.-]	CCM
2606916720	K02637	<i>petD</i> ; cytochrome b6-f complex subunit 4	Cytochrome b6-f
2606918059	K02634	<i>petA</i> ; apocytochrome f	Cytochrome b6-f
2606919766	K02636	<i>petC</i> ; cytochrome b6-f complex iron-sulfur subunit [EC:7.1.1.6]	Cytochrome b6-f
2606917943	K01601	<i>rbcL</i> , <i>cbbL</i> ; ribulose-bisphosphate carboxylase large chain [EC:4.1.1.39]	DIC fixation
2606917945	K08698	<i>ccmM</i> ; carbon dioxide concentrating mechanism protein CcmM	DIC fixation
2606918335	K00855	PRK, <i>prkB</i> ; phosphoribulokinase [EC:2.7.1.19]	DIC fixation
2606914850	K25026	<i>glk</i> ; glucokinase [EC:2.7.1.2]	Glycolysis
2606917561	K00845	<i>glk</i> ; glucokinase [EC:2.7.1.2]	Glycolysis
2606915553	K00927	PGK, <i>pgk</i> ; phosphoglycerate kinase [EC:2.7.2.3]	Glycolysis
2606919513	K15633	<i>gpmI</i> ; 2,3-bisphosphoglycerate-independent phosphoglycerate mutase [EC:5.4.2.12]	Glycolysis
2606916980	K13810	<i>tal-pgi</i> ; transaldolase / glucose-6-phosphate isomerase [EC:2.2.1.2 5.3.1.9]	Glycolysis
2606918128	K03841	FBP, <i>fbp</i> ; fructose-1,6-bisphosphatase I [EC:3.1.3.11]	Glycolysis

query_id	ko	gene_id	Metabolic & cellular functions
2606915989	K00873	PK, <i>pyk</i> ; pyruvate kinase [EC:2.7.1.40]	Glycolysis
2606916646	K21071	<i>pfk, pfp</i> ; ATP-dependent phosphofructokinase[EC:2.7.1.11 2.7.1.90]	Glycolysis
2606916647	K21071	<i>pfk, pfp</i> ; ATP-dependent phosphofructokinase[EC:2.7.1.11 2.7.1.90]	Glycolysis
2606919899	K01803	TPI, <i>tpiA</i> ; triosephosphate isomerase (TIM) [EC:5.3.1.1]	Glycolysis
2606919681	K01689	ENO, <i>eno</i> ; enolase [EC:4.2.1.11]	Glycolysis
2606919767	K00134	GAPDH, <i>gapA</i> ; glyceraldehyde 3-phosphate dehydrogenase (phosphorylating) [EC:1.2.1.12]	Glycolysis
2606920001	K00134	GAPDH, <i>gapA</i> ; glyceraldehyde 3-phosphate dehydrogenase (phosphorylating) [EC:1.2.1.12]	Glycolysis
2606920390	K00134	GAPDH, <i>gapA</i> ; glyceraldehyde 3-phosphate dehydrogenase (phosphorylating) [EC:1.2.1.12]	Glycolysis
2606914801	K02092	<i>apcA</i> ; allophycocyanin alpha subunit	Light harvesting
2606916561	K02092	<i>apcA</i> ; allophycocyanin alpha subunit	Light harvesting
2606917733	K02092	<i>apcA</i> ; allophycocyanin alpha subunit	Light harvesting
2606917734	K02092	<i>apcA</i> ; allophycocyanin alpha subunit	Light harvesting
2606919425	K02092	<i>apcA</i> ; allophycocyanin alpha subunit	Light harvesting
2606919788	K02092	<i>apcA</i> ; allophycocyanin alpha subunit	Light harvesting
2606920272	K02092	<i>apcA</i> ; allophycocyanin alpha subunit	Light harvesting
2606920273	K02092	<i>apcA</i> ; allophycocyanin alpha subunit	Light harvesting
2606920278	K02092	<i>apcA</i> ; allophycocyanin alpha subunit	Light harvesting
2606916563	K02094	<i>apcC</i> ; phycobilisome core linker protein	Light harvesting
2606915606	K02096	<i>apcE</i> ; phycobilisome core-membrane linker protein	Light harvesting
2606919782	K02096	<i>apcE</i> ; phycobilisome core-membrane linker protein	Light harvesting
2606916562	K02097	<i>apcF</i> ; phycobilisome core component	Light harvesting
2606914920	K02290	<i>cpcG</i> ; phycobilisome rod-core linker protein	Light harvesting
2606919571	K05378	<i>cpeC, mpeC</i> ; phycoerythrin-associated linker protein	Light harvesting
2606915605	K05379	<i>cpeD, mpeD</i> ; phycoerythrin-associated linker protein	Light harvesting
2606915604	K05382	<i>cpeS</i> ; phycoerythrin-associated linker protein	Light harvesting

query_id	ko	gene_id	Metabolic & cellular functions
2606919787	K05383	<i>cpeT</i> ; CpeT protein	Light harvesting
2606920271	K05384	<i>cpeU</i> , mpeU; bilin biosynthesis protein	Light harvesting
2606919786	K05385	<i>cpeY</i> ; bilin biosynthesis protein	Light harvesting
2606920276	K05386	<i>cpeZ</i> ; bilin biosynthesis protein	Light harvesting
2606920817	K08919	<i>pcbB</i> ; chlorophyll a/b binding light-harvesting protein PcbB	Light harvesting
2606920947	K08919	<i>pcbB</i> ; chlorophyll a/b binding light-harvesting protein PcbB	Light harvesting
2606920945	K08921	<i>pcbD</i> ; chlorophyll a/b binding light-harvesting protein PcbD	Light harvesting
2606917456	K02597	<i>nifZ</i> ; nitrogen fixation protein NifZ	N ₂ fixation
2606917461	K02585	<i>nifB</i> ; nitrogen fixation protein NifB	N ₂ fixation
2606917464	K02588	<i>nifH</i> ; nitrogenase iron protein NifH	N ₂ fixation
2606917465	K02586	<i>nifD</i> ; nitrogenase molybdenum-iron protein alpha chain [EC:1.18.6.1]	N ₂ fixation
2606917466	K02591	<i>nifK</i> ; nitrogenase molybdenum-iron protein beta chain [EC:1.18.6.1]	N ₂ fixation
2606917469	K02592	<i>nifN</i> ; nitrogenase molybdenum-iron protein NifN	N ₂ fixation
2606917470	K02592	<i>nifN</i> ; nitrogenase molybdenum-iron protein NifN	N ₂ fixation
2606917471	K02596	<i>nifX</i> ; nitrogen fixation protein NifX	N ₂ fixation
2606917474	K02595	<i>nifW</i> ; nitrogenase-stabilizing/protective protein	N ₂ fixation
2606919404	K02689	<i>psaA</i> ; photosystem I P700 chlorophyll a apoprotein A1	PS I
2606919405	K02689	<i>psaA</i> ; photosystem I P700 chlorophyll a apoprotein A1	PS I
2606919406	K02689	<i>psaA</i> ; photosystem I P700 chlorophyll a apoprotein A1	PS I
2606917291	K02692	<i>psaD</i> ; photosystem I subunit II	PS I
2606920752	K02693	<i>psaE</i> ; photosystem I subunit IV	PS I
2606914318	K02694	<i>psaF</i> ; photosystem I subunit III	PS I
2606914317	K02697	<i>psaJ</i> ; photosystem I subunit IX	PS I
2606914436	K02698	<i>psaK</i> ; photosystem I subunit X	PS I
2606915192	K08902	<i>psb27</i> ; photosystem II Psb27 protein	PS I

query_id	ko	gene_id	Metabolic & cellular functions
2606916161	K02703	<i>psbA</i> ; photosystem II P680 reaction center D1 protein [EC:1.10.3.9]	PS II
2606919382	K02703	<i>psbA</i> ; photosystem II P680 reaction center D1 protein [EC:1.10.3.9]	PS II
2606920731	K02705	<i>psbC</i> ; photosystem II CP43 chlorophyll apoprotein	PS II
2606917933	K02706	<i>psbD</i> ; photosystem II P680 reaction center D2 protein [EC:1.10.3.9]	PS II
2606919604	K02706	<i>psbD</i> ; photosystem II P680 reaction center D2 protein [EC:1.10.3.9]	PS II
2606920308	K02706	<i>psbD</i> ; photosystem II P680 reaction center D2 protein [EC:1.10.3.9]	PS II
2606920628	K02707	<i>psbE</i> ; photosystem II cytochrome b559 subunit alpha	PS II
2606918346	K02709	<i>psbH</i> ; photosystem II PsbH protein	PS II
2606915199	K02712	<i>psbK</i> ; photosystem II PsbK protein	PS II
2606916174	K02716	<i>psbO</i> ; photosystem II oxygen-evolving enhancer protein 1	PS II
2606918700	K02717	<i>psbP</i> ; photosystem II oxygen-evolving enhancer protein 2	PS II
2606920444	K02719	<i>psbU</i> ; photosystem II PsbU protein	PS II
2606917295	K02723	<i>psbY</i> ; photosystem II PsbY protein	PS II
2606916381	K02724	<i>psbZ</i> ; photosystem II PsbZ protein	PS II
2606920730	K08928	<i>pufL</i> ; photosynthetic reaction center L subunit	PS II
2606914520	K04077	<i>groEL</i> , HSPD1; chaperonin GroEL [EC:5.6.1.7]	Stress induced proteins
2606914623	K04062	<i>osmB</i> ; osmotically inducible lipoprotein OsmB	Stress induced proteins
2606914819	K04043	<i>dnaK</i> , HSPA9; molecular chaperone DnaK	Stress induced proteins
2606917170	K13993	HSP20; HSP20 family protein	Stress induced proteins
2606917268	K04079	HSP90A, <i>htpG</i> ; molecular chaperone HtpG	Stress induced proteins
2606918417	K13993	HSP20; HSP20 family protein	Stress induced proteins
2606919589	K04062	<i>osmB</i> ; osmotically inducible lipoprotein OsmB	Stress induced proteins
2606920266	K04077	<i>groEL</i> , HSPD1; chaperonin GroEL [EC:5.6.1.7]	Stress induced proteins
2606920267	K04078	<i>groES</i> , HSPE1; chaperonin GroES	Stress induced proteins
2606917932	K00382	DLD, <i>lpd</i> , <i>pdhD</i> ; dihydrolipoamide dehydrogenase [EC:1.8.1.4]	TCA

query_id	ko	gene_id	Metabolic & cellular functions
2606920327	K01903	<i>sucC</i> ; succinyl-CoA synthetase beta subunit [EC:6.2.1.5]	TCA
2606919672	K01679	<i>fumC</i> , FH; fumarate hydratase, class II [EC:4.2.1.2]	TCA
2606915237	K00024	<i>mdh</i> ; malate dehydrogenase [EC:1.1.1.37]	TCA

Supplementary Figures

Fig. S1. Cell-specific (A) DIC and (B) N₂ fixation rates in the different treatments, where each dot represents the uptake rate for single cells and boxplots show the 25–75th percentile, error bars the minimum and maximum percentile and the crossbar the median, respectively.

Fig. S2. (A) Percentage of active cells fixing DIC and N₂ in unamended conditions or (B) taking up DOC uptake and N₂ in DOM-amended conditions.

Fig. S3. Differentially expressed genes between treatments ($p < 0.01$; low vs. intermediate, low vs. extreme and intermediate vs. extreme) on days 2 and 4. Genes are grouped by common pathway or function (see Table S1 for gene full names and grouping). Genes are coloured by the treatment with higher expression for each pair-wise comparison (low in blue, intermediate in orange and extreme in pink). The size of the dot increases with increasing fold change. Genes showing no differences between treatments are coloured in grey.

Fig. S4. Differentially expressed genes between days 2 and 4 for each treatment. Genes are grouped by common pathway or function (see Table S1 for gene full names and grouping). Genes are coloured in purple when they are more expressed in day 2 than day 4 and in green otherwise. Genes showing no differences between treatments are coloured in grey. The size of the dot increases with increasing fold change.

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